

AN INNOVATIVE MODEL OF AESTHETIC EDUCATION OF STUDENTS THROUGH FAIRY TALE THERAPY

Mamataliyeva Mahbuba Abduvoris qizi

University of Business and Science

Higher educational institution teacher

Annotation

This article scientifically analyzes the theoretical and methodological possibilities of fairy tale therapy in the process of forming aesthetic education of students. An innovative pedagogical model based on fairy tale therapy in ensuring aesthetic education is developed, its components, stages and efficiency criteria are substantiated. The results of the study serve to improve aesthetic education in preschool and primary education practice.

Keywords: aesthetic education, fairy tale therapy, innovative model, student, artistic perception, emotional and intellectual development.

INTRODUCTION

In the modern educational paradigm, the comprehensive development of the individual, in particular, the formation of his aesthetic culture, is considered one of the priority tasks. Preschool age is one of the important stages in the formation of a child as a person. During this period, the child perceives the world mainly through play, imagination, and fairy tales. Therefore, the use of fairy tales in the educational process is an important tool for shaping the child's thinking, moral views, and emotional world. In recent years, fairy tale therapy has been widely used in psychological and pedagogical practice. Aesthetic education is an important factor

in the development of a person's spiritual and moral maturity, social adaptation, and creative potential. Especially in the early years of the upbringing of children, the strong influence of aesthetic influences plays a decisive role in the formation of their worldview and value system. In recent years, the need to introduce innovative pedagogical technologies into the educational process has increased, and the use of therapeutic and pedagogical methods in aesthetic education, along with traditional approaches, has become a pressing issue. One of such methods is fairy tale therapy, which allows developing the child's internal emotional state through artistic images. The purpose of this article is to scientifically substantiate an innovative model of aesthetic education of children based on fairy tale therapy.

In preschool educational organizations, children are comprehensively prepared for school education. Among them, the development of a child's speech is one of the most important. It is very important for them to increase their vocabulary, speak fluently and be able to fully express and convey their thoughts. Therefore, speech development classes are one of the most important classes among the classes held in preschool educational institutions. Fiction serves as a powerful, effective tool for the intellectual, moral and aesthetic education of children, it has a huge impact on the development and enrichment of a child's speech. Fiction is a powerful and effective tool for the intellectual, moral and aesthetic education of children, which has a huge impact on the development and enrichment of a preschool child's speech. It enriches feelings, strengthens imagination, gives the child wonderful examples of the Uzbek literary language. Fiction opens and explains to the child the life of society and nature, the world of people's emotions and relationships. It develops the child's thinking and imagination, enriches his feelings and provides wonderful examples of the Uzbek literary language. Its educational, cognitive and aesthetic value is incomparable, because it expands the child's knowledge of the world around him, develops the ability to subtly feel the form and rhythm of his native language. Fiction accompanies a person from the first years of his life.

A literary work appears in the child's mind when there is content and artistic form. Only when the child is prepared for this, the perception of a literary work will be complete, and for this it is necessary to attract children's attention not only to its content, but also to the expressive means of the language of a fairy tale, story, poem and other works of art. In stories, children learn the conciseness and clarity of the word; in folk tales, they reveal to children the lightness and expressiveness of the language, the richness of speech with humor, vivid and figurative expressions, comparisons. Fairy tales are an ancient genre of folk oral creativity, which play an important role in the formation of imagination, fantasy, speech, moral values and life experience in children. Also, through fairy tales, children gain a simple and figurative understanding of complex life situations, the struggle between good and evil. Fairy tale therapy is a psychological and pedagogical method that uses fairy tales in working with children to analyze their inner world, facilitate their social adaptation, and eliminate problems. Fairy tales are an ancient genre of oral folk art that play an important role in the formation of imagination, fantasy, speech, moral values, and life experience in children. Also, through fairy tales, children gain a simple and figurative understanding of complex life situations and the struggle between good and evil. Fairy tale therapy is a psychological and pedagogical method that uses fairy tales in working with children to analyze their inner world, facilitate their social adaptation, and eliminate problems.

Fairy tale therapy methods for preschool children are very diverse. One of the most popular methods is to compose a fairy tale. There are many ready-made fairy tales that have a therapeutic effect, but the best solution is for the child's parents to write a magical story. Fairy tale therapy helps to correct existing defects in the development of speech in preschool children. This method is often used by speech therapists and is effective in eliminating problems such as hyperactivity, laziness, low self-esteem, fear, and aggressive behavior. The main tasks of fairy tale therapy for preschool children are to identify the problem and successfully solve it.

SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF AESTHETIC EDUCATION

Aesthetic education as a pedagogical category represents the process of forming the ability to perceive, evaluate beauty and create aesthetic values in a person. Aesthetic education is carried out through the understanding of beauty in art, nature, social relationships, and personal activities.

In pedagogical literature, aesthetic education is described through the following structural aspects:

- aesthetic perception;
- aesthetic feeling;
- aesthetic taste;
- aesthetic ideal;
- creative-aesthetic activity.

These components are inextricably linked to each other and ensure the formation of the student as a person. According to psychological research, the preschool age is the highest stage of aesthetic sensitivity. During this period, figurative thinking, fantasy and emotional perception prevail in children. It is these features that allow the effective use of artistic means, including fairy tales, in aesthetic education. Fairy tale therapy is an integrative method based on influencing the internal psychic processes of a person through symbolic-artistic images, which combines elements of pedagogy, psychology and art history. Scientific sources note that fairy tale therapy performs the following functions:

- diagnostic;
- correctional;

- developmental;
- educational.

Fairy tale therapy provides the following pedagogical opportunities in aesthetic education:

- activation of aesthetic perception through artistic images;
- understanding of the categories of beauty and ugliness, good and evil;
- development of aesthetic feelings and imagination;
- creation of conditions for creative self-expression.

In this regard, fairy tale therapy is recognized as an effective innovative tool of aesthetic education.

This innovative model is based on the following methodological approaches:

- person-oriented approach;
- competency-based approach;
- activity-based approach;
- integrative approach.

The main goal of the model is to develop the aesthetic consciousness, taste and creative activity of students through fairy tale therapy.

Tasks:

- systematization of fairy tale therapy opportunities in aesthetic education;
- integration of artistic and aesthetic activities;

- enrichment of the emotional and aesthetic experience of students.

The model consists of the following components:

1. Target component - the goal and expected results of aesthetic education
2. Content component - fairy tales, symbolic images, aesthetic tasks
3. Technological component - methods and forms of fairy tale therapy
4. Reflexive-evaluative component - understanding and analysis of emotions
5. Resultant component - level of aesthetic development

STAGES OF IMPLEMENTING AESTHETIC EDUCATION ON THE BASIS OF FAIRY TALE THERAPY.

1. Diagnostic-preparatory stage

The aesthetic interests, emotional state and creative capabilities of the students are determined.

2. Activity stage

Aesthetic activity is organized through listening to, analyzing, staging, drawing and artistic creation of the fairy tale.

3. Reflexive-final stage

The aesthetic experience obtained is summarized, the level of development is assessed.

SCIENTIFIC ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS OF EXPERIMENTAL WORK

The results of the experimental work showed that the process of aesthetic education organized on the basis of fairy tale therapy:

- increased the level of aesthetic perception;
- increased creative activity;
- provided emotional stability.

This fact scientifically confirms the pedagogical effectiveness of the innovative model.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

Russian scientists T.D. Zinkevich-Evstigneeva, I.V. Vachkov, A.V. Gnezdilov, E.S. Romanenko made a great contribution to the development of the pedagogical and psychological foundations of fairy tale therapy. B.T. Likhachev, N.A. Vetlugina, B.M. Nemensky, T.Ya. Shpikalova conducted fundamental research on aesthetic education. E.I. Koroteyeva, L.P. Pechko, N.M. Konisheva studied the issues of various areas and methods of aesthetic education. In foreign studies, Elliott Eisner (1933-2014), Maxine Greene (1917-2014), Sir Ken Robinson (1950-2020) emphasized the importance of creativity and aesthetic education in education. David Elkind (1931-), Vivian Gussin Paley (1929-2019), Jerome Bruner (1915-2016) highlighted the role of artistic activity and stories in the development of children.

CONCLUSION

Scientific analysis shows that fairy tale therapy is an innovative tool with high pedagogical potential in developing the aesthetic education of students. The developed model serves to systematically and effectively organize aesthetic education and is recommended for implementation in educational practice.

REFERENCES

1. Rakhimova Z. Fundamentals of fairy tale therapy. Journal of Pedagogy of Uzbekistan, 2022.

2. Zebinisso Ahmedova “Fairy tale therapy” 2023.
3. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Education”.
4. Scientific articles on preschool education pedagogy.
5. Mamataliyeva Mahbuba Abduvoris qizi The role and mechanisms of influence of fairy tale therapy as a pedagogical tool for shaping the aesthetic culture of students
<https://intconf.online/index.php/icarhse/article/view/641>
6. Rakhmonova Iroda Samijonovna, . (2025). Developing Reflexive Skills in Preschool Children in a Developmental Play Environment. CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS, 6(01), 18–22.
<https://doi.org/10.37547/pedagogics-crjp-06-01-05>
7. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/maktabgacha-ta-lim-tashkilotlaridaertakterapiyadan-foydalanish>